

Nivel de pertinencia de los artículos

(Artículos seleccionados)

REVISTA	NOMBRE	CLARIDAD	RIGOR	RELEVANCIA	CREDIBILIDAD	PROM	NIVEL
IEEE	Quantum-Key-Distribution-Based Microgrid Control for Cybersecurity Enhancement	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
ACM	ExSol: Collaboratively Assessing Cybersecurity Risks for Protecting Energy Delivery Systems	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
ACM	Goosewolf: An Embedded Intrusion Detection System for Advanced Programmable Logic Controllers	1	1	0,5	1	3,5	Alta
ACM	How Should Enterprises Quantify and Analyze (Multi-Party) APT Cyber-Risk Exposure in their Industrial IoT Network?	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
ACM	Autonomous and Adaptive Cyber Incident Detection and Response in Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems using Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning	1	1	0,8	1	3,8	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A critical review on intelligent-based techniques for detection and mitigation of cyberthreats and cascaded failures in cyber-physical power systems	1	1	0,8	1	3,8	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	A systemic framework for addressing cybersecurity in construction	1	1	0,9	1	3,9	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	How could quantum computing shape information systems research – An editorial perspective and future research directions	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Securing SCADA systems in smart grids with IoT integration: A Self-Defensive Post-Quantum Blockchain Architecture	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A survey on quantum-safe blockchain security infrastructure	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A quantum-based approach for offensive security against cyber attacks in electrical infrastructure	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	FedCognis: An Adaptive Federated Learning Framework for Secure Anomaly Detection in Industrial IoT-Enabled Cognitive Cities	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Quantum-Inspired Blockchain-Based Cybersecurity: Securing Smart Edge Utilities in IoT-Based Smart Cities	1	1	9	1	3,9	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	Unraveling the dynamics of the cyber threat landscape: Major shifts examined through the recent societal events	1	1	8	1	3,8	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Edge-Fog Enhanced Post-Quantum Network Security: Applications, Challenges and Solutions	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Securing financial sector applications in the quantum era: a comprehensive evaluation of NIST's recommended algorithms through use-case analysis	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Evaluation framework for quantum security risk assessment: A comprehensive strategy for quantum-safe transition	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A lightweight BRLWE-based post-quantum cryptosystem with side-channel resilience for IoT security	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A practical study of post-quantum enhanced identity-based encryption	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	IHKEM: A post-quantum ready hierarchical key establishment and management scheme for wireless sensor networks	1	1	1	1	4	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	Hybrid and adaptive framework for secure and scalable authentication in healthcare IoT	1	1	9	1	3,9	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Exploring coverage and security challenges in wireless sensor networks: A survey	1	1	9	1	3,9	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Realizing quantum-safe information sharing: Implementation and adoption challenges and policy recommendations for quantum-safe transitions	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Mitigating 5G security challenges for next-gen industry using quantum computing	1	9	1	1	3,8	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Quantum-Resistant Cryptographic Primitives Using Modular Hash Learning Algorithms for Enhanced SCADA System Security	1	9	1	1	3,8	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Securing Modbus in legacy industrial control systems: A decentralized approach using proxies, Post-Quantum Cryptography and Self-Sovereign Identity	1	1	1	1	4	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	Quantum secure authentication and key agreement protocols for IoT-enabled applications: A comprehensive survey and open challenges	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Embracing the quantum frontier: Investigating quantum communication, cryptography, applications and future directions	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Cyber resilience in e-governance: A review of strategies, challenges, and directions	1	0,9	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Evaluation of hardware and software implementations for NIST finalist and fourth-round post-quantum cryptography KEMs	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Quantum-resilient blockchain-enabled secure communication framework for connected autonomous vehicles using post-quantum cryptography	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	A scientometric analysis of quantum driven innovations in intelligent transportation systems	1	1	1	1	4	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	PureQuantum: Towards A Scalable Blockchain Channel Security in IoT Networks	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Cybersecurity in smart microgrids using blockchain-federated learning and quantum-safe approaches: A comprehensive review	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	AI-based cybersecurity for a sustainable digital industry: Systematic literature review and future research directions	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Critical component analysis of cyber-physical power systems in cascading failures using graph convolutional networks: An energy-based approach	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	An approach for assessing the functional vulnerabilities criticality of CPS components	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
SCIENCEDIRECT	Analysis of safety and security challenges and opportunities related to cyber-physical systems	1	1	1	1	4	Alta

SCIENCEDIRECT	Multi-aspect rule-based AI: Methods, taxonomy, challenges and directions towards automation, intelligence and transparent cybersecurity modeling for critical infrastructures	1	1	1	1	4	Alta
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